

Generalized Oscillator Propagators and Transformations

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Mar. 23. 2021

In (1) (which does not deal with propagators), a transformation $\exp[i a/2 (pp + xx)]$ where $a=3.14/2$ is introduced to convert an oscillator potential with time-dependent mass $H= a(t)pp + xx$ into one with constant mass and a time-dependent spring constant $H= pp + a(t)xx$. Given that it is straightforward to obtain the propagator for the second case (using classical equations of motion), one might consider transforming this propagator back to the time dependent mass situation. A problem which may arise, however, is that the form of the propagator in both cases is: $Q(t) \exp[i (b(t)XX + g1(t)XY + g2(t)YY)]$ and the transformation may disrupt this form. To consider this in more detail, we consider $H= pp + xx$ and see that the transformation takes the wavefunction $W= a1 \exp(-iE1 t) W1(x) + a2 \exp(-iE2 t) W2(x)$ and adds energy dependent phases $FW = W= a1 \exp(-iE1 t) \exp(-iaE1) W1(x) + a2 \exp(-iE2 t) W2(x) \exp(-iaE2)$. Given that $Ei = (n+.5)$, the phases differ and one no longer has a propagator. Thus, when dealing with propagators which are a solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation, one must be careful about the form of the propagator, it seems. A transformed propagator is still a solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation, but not necessarily still a propagator.

Oscillator Propagators

In (2), a general recipe for calculating generalized oscillator propagators $H= a(t)pp + k(t)xx$ is given. First, one assumes the form:

$$K = \text{propagator} = Q(t) \exp[i (b(t)XX + g1(t)XY + g2(t)YY)] \quad ((1))$$

This is an important restriction which must be maintained.

Secondly, K is inserted into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation and coefficients of XX, XY etc equated. This leads to a set of differential equations yielding Q(t) (from a pure imaginary match), b(t), g1(t) and g2(t). In particular, (2) lists:

$$db/dt + 4a(t)bb + k(t) = 0 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{where } H= a(t)pp + b(t)xx \quad ((2b))$$

H may be generalized to contain $-i c(t) W dW/dx$ and even linear terms, although ((2)) changes in such a case.

Thus, by solving the differential equation ((2b)), one may obtain a solution for the case of both a time-dependent mass and spring constant.

Alternatively, one may use:

$$K= Q(t) \exp(i Sc) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } Sc = \text{classical action} = \text{Integral } dt1 (0, t) L \quad \text{where } L \text{ is the Lagrangian.}$$

Care must be made so that $H = dL/(d dx/dt) dx/dt - L$. In the case of $a(t) = 1$ and $b(t)$ i.e. constant mass, but a time-dependent spring constant, one may solve the Lagrangian and find a solution related to the classical equations of motions i.e.:

$$b(t) = \text{constant } dA/dt / A \text{ where } A(t) \text{ is a classical solution of motion } ((4))$$

In (1), a transformation F is given which changes $H = a(t)pp + xx$ into $F^{-1}HF = H_1 = pp + a(t) xx$. Thus, one may think that one may solve for the constant mass, time-dependent spring constant propagator ((4)) and then take the transform $F^{-1}K$ to obtain the propagator for the constant spring constant, time-dependent mass case. (A problem which may occur, however, is that the transformation may change the form of the propagator, while still keeping $F^{-1}K$ as a solution to the time-dependent Schrodinger equation.

Transformation $\exp[i (pp+xx)]$

As shown in (1), $F = \exp[i (pp+xx)]$ transforms $H = a(t)pp + xx$ into $H_1 = pp + a(t) xx$.

To obtain this result, the relations are used:

$$\exp[i a/2 (pp+xx)] x \exp[- i a/2 (pp+xx)] = \cos(a)x - p \sin(a) \text{ and}$$

$$\exp[i a/2 (pp+xx)] p \exp[- i a/2 (pp+xx)] = \sin(a)x + p \cos(a) \quad ((5))$$

These may be obtained using $pp+aa = (a+) a^{-1}$ and $x = [a - (a+)]$ where $a = p+ix$ and $(a+) = p-ix$.

$$\text{Then } [(at)a^{-1}] a = a \{ (a+)a^{-1} + 2 \} \text{ and } - \{ (a+)a^{-1} \} (a+) = -(a+)\{ (a+)a^{-1} - 2 \}.$$

$$\text{With these results: } a(t) F^{-1}pF F^{-1}p F = a(t) \{ \sin(a)x + p \cos(a) \} \{ \sin(a)x + p \cos(a) \} \quad ((6a))$$

$$F^{-1}xF F^{-1}x F = \{ \cos(a)x - p \sin(a) \} \{ \cos(a)x - p \sin(a) \} \quad ((6b))$$

Using $a = 3.14/2$ eliminates p from ((6)) and transfers $a(t)$ to xx $\sin(a)\sin(a) = xx$.

$F^{-1}xF F^{-1}x F = pp$. In other words, the coefficient of pp is transferred to xx and vice versa.

Thus, one may transform $H = a(t)pp + x$ into $H = pp + a(t)xx$.

Transformation $\exp[i (pp+xx)]$ and Phases

The above scenario with the transformation F used to convert the Hamiltonian from one form into another must be treated with care. If W is a solution of the transformed Hamiltonian, then $F^{-1}W$ is a solution of the original one, however, if W is a propagator, $F^{-1}W$ may no longer be one.

To see this, consider the simple example: $H = p^2 + x^2$ ((7)).

In such a case, the transformed Hamiltonian is the same as ((7)), but there is a propagator solution K to ((7)) and also $F^{-1}K$ which is a solution to $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} W = H W$, but no longer a propagator. To see this consider:

$$K(x,t,x_1) = \sum_n \exp(-iE_n t) W_n^*(x_1) W_n(x) \quad ((8))$$

If one has $W_0(x_1) = W_3(x_1) + W_4(x_1)$ then:

$$\int dx_1 K(x,t,x_1) (W_3(x_1) + W_4(x_1)) = \exp(-E_3 t) W_3(x) + \exp(-E_4 t) W_4(x).$$

Here W_n is a solution of $E_n W_n = H W_n$ ((9)). Thus, $\exp[i \frac{3.14}{4} (p^2 + x^2)] = \exp(i \frac{3.14}{4} E_n)$. In such a case: $\exp(i \frac{a}{2} (p^2 + x^2)) K(x,t,x_1)$ adds different phases to different W_n i.e.

$$\int dx_1 \exp(i \frac{a}{2} (p^2 + x^2)) K(x,t,x_1) (W_3(x_1) + W_4(x_1)) = \exp[i \frac{3.14}{4} (3 + .5)] \exp(-E_3 t) W_3(x) + \exp[i \frac{3.14}{4} (4 + .5)] \exp(-E_4 t) W_4(x) \text{ because } E_n = (n + .5) \text{ for } H = p^2 + x^2.$$

The two phases introduced are not the same, so $F^{-1}K$, although still being a solution of the time dependent Schrodinger equation is no longer a propagator. This suggests it may not have the form $Q(t) \exp[i (b(t)XX + g_1(t)XY + g_2(t)YY)]$ because such a form, when inserted into the Schrodinger equation followed by the equation of coefficients of XX etc yields the propagator solution. Interestingly $F^{-1}F^{-1}K$ yields the propagator back. I.e. One flips coefficients of p and x and then flips them back again.

Thus, when dealing with propagators, one must be careful about transforming a Hamiltonian, solving for the propagator of the transformed H and transforming back. We suggest this may be the case for $H = a(t)p^2 + x^2$ being transformed to $H_1 = p^2 + a(t)x^2$. The propagator for H_1 is of the form:

$$K_1 = Q(t) \exp[i (b(t)XX + g_1(t)XY + g_2(t)YY)] \text{ where } b(t) = .5 \frac{dA/dt}{A} \text{ where } A(t) \text{ is a solution of the classical equations of motion: } \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} = -k(t)A \quad ((10))$$

Given this solution, $F^{-1}K_1 = \exp[i \frac{3.14}{4} (-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + x^2)] K_1$, but this operation may destroy the $\exp(i b(t)XX + \text{etc})$ form of the propagator and simply yield a non-propagator solution to the time-dependent Schrodinger equation.

In both the case of H and H_1 , the propagator is of the form $Q(t) \exp[i (b(t)XX + g_1(t)XY + g_2(t)YY)]$, but $\frac{db}{dt} = 4a(t)bb + 1$ for the first scenario and $\frac{db}{dt} = 4bb + a(t)$ for the second.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is possible use the transformation $\exp[i \frac{3.14}{4} (p^2 + x^2)]$ to switch coefficients of $H = a(t)p^2 + k(t)x^2$ i.e. $\rightarrow H_1 = k(t)p^2 + a(t)x^2$. In particular if $k(t)=1$, the switch may change a time dependent mass, constant spring constant into a constant mass, time-dependent spring

constant which is readily solvable for the propagator K_1 . Using $F^{-1}K_1$ to transform back, yields a solution to the time-dependent Schrodinger equation, but not necessarily a propagator as we show for the $H=pp+xx$ case. The form $\exp[i (b(t)XX + g_1(t)XY + g_2(t) YY)]$ may be altered through $F^{-1}K_1$. Thus, transformations are useful for solutions of the Schrodinger equation, but necessarily for the propagator, which though being a solution, has further restrictions.

References

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